

School Head's Conflict Resolution Skills in Relation to Teachers Performance

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Abstract:

This study directed to determine School Heads' conflict resolution skills levels in terms of Amicable Settlement, negotiation and reprimand in relation to teachers' performance. Determine the significant difference in the School Heads' level of conflict management skills when grouped and compared according to age, sex, plantilla position and highest educational attainment. This research employed descriptive research design to obtain information concerning on the different areas cited and to describe what exists with respect to different variables identified herein. Results shows high level of school heads' of conflict management skills when grouped and compared according to the different areas cited and in terms of aforementioned variables. Also, teacher's performance level in terms of variables shows very satisfactory result. Lastly, there is no significant relationship between the school heads' level of conflict resolution skills and the level of teacher's performance. From findings, this paper calls for school leaders to assess the strategic management skills of the principal to ensure effective teaching methods are implemented by all teachers, school principal to focus on teaching and learning in classes, develop themselves and go for further studies, and must be a good listener.

Keywords: School head's conflict resolution skills, amicable settlement, negotiation, reprimand, teacher's performance, plantilla position, and highest academic attainment.

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Conflict at work is inevitable; however, the result may be influenced by how the conflict is managed. The volume and intensity of impending conflict are determined by how the conflict is handled (Howell, 2014). Effective school leaders encourage collective cultures. Schools need dedicated, value-led, competent, and highly motivated leaders who can encourage reflective practice and foster dialogue and cooperation among all school actors and stakeholders. They ensure a supportive environment for teachers, where teacher-teacher learning, time for feedback and reflection, and networking within and between schools are encouraged. School leaders should be able to portion authority by dispensing management roles inside the school. In a 'distributed leadership' model, leadership, teaching, and non-teaching staff, learners, as well as parents and families, are invigorated to take on leading roles in a particular area of expertise, to assume accountability, and independently or as part of a group, to take ingenuity. Chances for more stretchy working associations are created.

As observed in various schools and personal experiences as a public senior high school teacher, conflicts experienced such as imbalanced work distributions among personnel, financial resources, in and out of class teaching activities and practices, personal disagreements between employees, competition at work, frustration with work and social demands, bullying and harassments are among the top prevalent concerns of most school heads.

This study is hypothesized to do a deeper investigation as to the degree of conflicts encountered, degree of resolutions experience, and the extent of experience in the work environment that individual teachers encountered in the education setting at identified schools for the school year 2022-2023 as bases for capacity- building plan.

Current State of Knowledge

Conflict in the workplace is inevitable; it happens in every organization and at every level (Howard, 2015). No one is immune to workplace conflict, it affects each individual differently, and each handle it differently. Charging

employees with the task of working together to achieve an organization's goals and mission often produces areas of disagreement that have the potential to turn into workplace conflict. These workplace conflicts either present positively or negatively. A positive workplace conflict can present opportunities for organizations through the emerging dialogue, often producing creative problem-solving by challenging workers to expand their thinking and dig beyond obvious solutions. Negative workplace conflicts can distract employees, causing them to focus on the conflict rather than the work they are hired to do.

As noted by (Adhia mbo, 2011), conflict brings stress and discomfort due to the fear of the unknown; hence, it is a depressing and frustrating state of affairs between the parties involved.

Conflict affects the smooth running of the teaching and learning process, but if carefully examined and managed, it leads to (Ramani & Zhimin, 2010) peaceful coexistence between teachers and their school leaders. However, conflict is inevitable; in principle, all conflicts cannot be resolved and managed.

Conflict, a social phenomenon between or among individuals, groups, organizations, and nations (Rubin, 1994), is an inseparable part of human and social life. Conflict, which is a process that occurs when an individual or a group realizes that their interests are obstructed or negatively influenced by others (Wall & Callister, 1995), is experienced because of disagreements and inconsistencies during interpersonal interactions (Rahim, 1983). The conflict, which may occur because of various reasons between two or more persons or in a group (Koçel, 2003), consists of deliberately planned acts to prevent success in achieving goals (Taştan, 2004). As can be seen from the definitions, conflict is regarded as a negative situation and a process. At the same time, difficulties are experienced in selecting among options, and deficiencies in decision-making mechanisms are observed in this process (Can, 2002). In general, conflict is a two-dimensional dynamic process that needs to be perceived by the parties, and there are difficulties in this process of selecting from among two or more options. The reasons for conflicts are disagreements, differences, friction, and discrepancies based on differences of opinion, views, and interests (İpek, 2000; Soyalp, 2001).

Conflicts, destructive phenomena to be avoided according to traditional views, are positive forces and necessary for organizations today to continue their existence (Robbins & Judge, 2012). Conflicts are not desired and generate failure simply because they need to be managed better, generating negative results. Therefore, the focus should be on how to manage the process instead of how to define it as a concept.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is hinged on the Contingency theory by Lex Donaldson (2015). Morton Deutsch's Theory of Conflict Resolution by Teachers College (2009) and the Hierarchy of Needs Theory by Pandey (2017). Contingency theory explains that the complexity of today imposes challenges to the exercise of leadership; organizations of all sizes are made up of people with sufficient autonomy to create their greatness, and leaders have to make it sustainable by aligning the interests of all members with the vision, mission, and values of such organizations. Hellesøy BT (2012). Leadership styles always evolve according to the context leader's face, with newer elements complementing, perfecting, and accompanying more traditional styles. With the right behavior, leaders have the best opportunities to succeed because a particular kind of performance in a particular context could encourage employees to share their creative ideas and opinions, provide a clear direction to accomplish purposes and objectives, and appeal to show the highest commitment with the outcome expected of their action Gundersen (2012). On the other hand, Morton Deutsch's Theory of Conflict Resolution explains that conflict resolution as a field of study formed hypothetical bits of knowledge about the nature and source of conflict and how conflicts are resolved through peaceful systems to effectuate a dependable settlement.

Teachers College (2009), this theory was the first to form an understanding of the helpful results of collaboration as a scholastic inquiry. Variables like the objectives in every group in a conflict in deciding the introduction a group would convey to the negotiation in order to reveal the conflict; it contends that when an individual or group is denied its major requirement for identity, security, acknowledgment, or equivalent investment inside of a public, extended conflict is inescapable. To determine such conflict, debilitated needs must be distinguished. Along these lines, rebuilding of connections or the social framework happens in a way that the needs of all people and groups are appropriate. The Theory of the Hierarchy of Needs defines need as a physiological or psychological deficiency a person feels compelled to satisfy. Pandey (2017), this need can create tensions that influence a person's work attitudes and behaviors. Furthermore, this theory explains that based on the definition of need proposes that humans are motivated by multiple needs and that these needs exist in a hierarchical order. This theory posits that only an unsatisfied need can influence behavior; a satisfied need is not a motivator. A person starts at the bottom of the hierarchy (pyramid) and will initially seek to satisfy basic needs (e.g., food, shelter). Once these physiological needs have been satisfied, they are no longer a motivator. The individual moves up to the next level. These three mentioned theories mainly back-up the present study, allowing the researcher to push through with the unfurling of answers based on the specific objectives raised in this study.

Objectives

This study aims to determine School Heads' conflict resolution skills levels in relation to teachers' performance in a District, in a fifth-class component city, in medium-sized schools division during the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, this study sought to determine: 1) the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, plantilla position, and highest educational attainment; 2) level of conflict resolution skills according to the following areas: amicable settlement, negotiation, reprimand when grouped and compared according to sex, age, plantilla position and highest educational attainment; 3) the level of conflict resolution skills when grouped according to the aforementioned variables; 4) the level of teachers' performance during the school year 2022-2023; 5) level of teachers' performance when grouped according to the aforementioned variables; 6) significant difference in the school heads' level of conflict resolution skills when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; 7) significant difference in the level of teacher performance when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; and 8) significant relationship between the school heads' level of conflict management skills and the level of teachers' performance.

Research Methodology

This section presents the research design used, the locale, the subjects, the respondents of the study, the research instruments, the conduct of the study, the procedure in the analysis of the data relative to the specific objectives, and the statistical tools used in the study.

Research Design

This study used the descriptive research design in determining the level of effectiveness and significant difference between SHS Teacher's and Administrators' conflict management styles of identified schools of a medium-sized division for the school year 2022-2023. According to Best and Kahn (2016), descriptive research is a method of research that concerns itself with the present phenomena in terms of conditions, practices, beliefs, processes, relationships, or trends. Descriptive research is devoted to the gathering of information about prevailing conditions or situations for description and interpretation. Said otherwise, descriptive research is defined as a purposive process of gathering, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating data about prevailing conditions, practices, beliefs, processes, trends, and cause-and-effect relationships and then making adequate and accurate interpretations about such information with or without the help of statistical methods. It also sought to determine differences between or among study variables, explore causes of phenomena, test hypotheses, and develop generalizations, principles, or theories based on findings. While its primary concerns are the conditions and things that exist at the study's time, it also considers past events and influences that are deemed related to what is studied in the present. The nature of this study determined the condition of things in their present state. It delved into the relationship between or among variables considered in the study and the influence of one variable on another. Based on the above premise, the researcher considered it most appropriate to use the descriptive research design.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 80 Senior High school teachers of the identified schools of a medium-sized schools division for the school year 2022-2023 who have been invited to participate and have taken part in this study. These teachers were considered as the respondents of this study.

Instruments

The researcher used a self-made survey questionnaire to find out the level of school heads' mentoring skills and leadership approaches. The questionnaire consists of two (2) parts: Part I is about the personal profile of the respondent, such as age, sex, plantilla position, and highest educational attainment. Part II gathers data on the school heads' level of conflict resolution skills in areas of amicable settlement, negotiations, and reprimand. There were five (5) questions in each of the areas under the level of school head's conflict resolution skills. Each item was rated on a scale of 1 to 5, using a 5-point Likert scale with five (5) as always, four (4) as often, three (3) as sometimes, two (2) as rarely, and one (1) as almost never.

Data Collection

After the research instrument was found valid and reliable, the researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent and then channeled to the Public Schools District Supervisor of Districts for the conduct of the study. After the approval, the questionnaires were distributed to the respondents, who were the teachers of all Districts. The data collected are tallied and carefully analyzed, and interpreted using appropriate statistical tools.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used the descriptive-analytical scheme and frequency count and percentage were used to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, plantilla position, and highest educational attainment.

Objective No. 2 used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean as a statistical tool to determine the level of conflict resolution skills according to the following areas: amicable settlement, negotiation and reprimand when group and compared according to age, sex, highest educational attainment.

Objective No. 3 also used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean as statistical tools to determine the level of conflict resolution skills when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective no. 4 also used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean as statistical tools to determine the level teachers' performance during the school year 2022-2023.

Objective no. 5 used the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test as a statistical tool to determine the significant difference in the level of level of teachers' performance when grouped according to when grouped according to age, sex, plantilla position, and highest educational attainment.

Objective no. 6 also used the same analytical scheme and statistical tools to determine the significant difference in the school heads' level of conflict resolution skills when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective no. 7 also used the same analytical scheme and statistical tools to determine the significant difference in the level of teacher performance when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. Finally,

Objective no. 8 also used the same analytical scheme and statistical tools to determine the significant difference in the level of significant relationship between the school heads' level of conflict management skills and the level of teachers' performance.

Ethical Consideration

Research Ethics Protocols are the principles that must be followed in conducting any type of research. Research ethics protocol makes sure that no human rights are violated and research being conducted has no hidden agenda (Fleming, 2018). To ensure the protection of the participants of the study, the researcher gave importance to the respondents' voluntary participation, informed consent, risk of harm, confidentiality, and anonymity. In this study, for voluntary participation, the researcher was asked to sign or agree to a consent form by filling out a blank line/data entry slot with respondents' initials or alias. However, they are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason. For informed consent, the research ensured that the respondents are fully informed about the procedures and risks involved in research and must give their consent to participate. For risk of harm, the researcher did not put participants in a situation where they might be at risk of harm because of their participation. If should this happen, the participants can decline to answer all the questions and may withdraw their participation at any time. For confidentiality, the researcher guaranteed the participants identifying information will not be made available to anyone who is not directly involved in the study. Further, for the anonymity of the respondents, the respondents used alias or initials to keep his/her identity anonymous to the researcher and other participants.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data that were gathered consistent with its predetermined objectives.

Table 1
Profile of the Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (Below 35 years old)	36	45.00
	Older (35 years old and above)	44	55.00
Sex	Male	23	28.70
	Female	57	71.30
Plantilla Position	Lower (T1)	41	51.20

Highest Attainment	Educational	Higher (T2 and above)	39	48.80
		Lower (Bachelor's Degree)	60	75.00
		Higher (Master's/Doctoral Degree)	20	25.00
		Total	80	100.00

As revealed in Table 1, Table No. 2 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of age; sex, plantilla position, and highest educational attainment. As to age, young or below 35 years old had a frequency of 36 or 45.00 percent while older or 35 years old had 44 or 55.00 percent. This means that there are older teachers than younger teachers actively participating in the research venue.

With regard to sex, 23 or 28.70 percent were male teachers while 57 or 71.30 percent were female teachers. This implies that there are more female teachers actively participating in recognizing the effectiveness of school heads' conflict management and conflict resolution skills than male in the research venue.

As to plantilla position, 41 or 51.20 percent belonged to lower position while 39 or 48.80 belonged to higher plantilla position. This means that lower plantilla position dominate than higher position as far as research venue is concerned.

With regard to highest educational attainment, 60 or 75.00 percent belonged to lower while 20 or 25.00 percent belonged to higher educational attainment group.

Table 2
School Heads' Level of Conflict Resolution Skills in the Areas of Amicable Settlement, Negotiation and Reprimand

Areas	Mean	Interpretation
A. Amicable Settlement		
1. Investigates an issue/problem in the new normal with the subordinates to find an acceptable solution.	4.39	High Level
2. Integrates ideas with those of the subordinates to come up with a decision jointly.	4.43	High Level
3. Works with subordinates to find a solution to a problem in the new normal that satisfies them expectations.	4.49	High Level
4. Collaborates with the subordinates to come up with decisions acceptable to them.	4.46	High Level
5. Works with the subordinates for a proper understanding of a problem in the new normal.	4.46	High Level
Sub-mean	4.39	High Level
B. Negotiation		
1. Negotiates with subordinates so that a compromise can be reached.	4.46	High Level
2. Conforms to the suggestions of the subordinates that may help in resolving problems.	4.49	High Level
3. Proposes a middle ground for breaking deadlocks	4.39	High Level
4. Uses "give and take" so that a compromise can be made.	4.41	High Level
5. Satisfies the needs of the subordinates with regards conflict resolution.	4.39	High Level
Sub-mean	4.43	High Level
C. Reprimand		
1. Calls the attention of teacher/staff once there is a complaint from a parent or stakeholders to talk with you about it.	4.48	High Level
2. Consults with teacher/staff regarding a matter which could lead to disciplinary action or suspension.	4.48	High Level
3. Initiates a private conference with teacher/staff with conflicts with colleagues.	4.41	High Level
4. Writes a memorandum to reprimand habitually committed errors.	4.13	High Level
5. Sets disobedient teacher/staff as top priority before submitting for terminal decision for grave offense to the higher office.	4.01	High Level
Sub-mean	4.30	High Level
Overall Mean	4.39	High Level

Table No. 2, reflects the school heads' level of conflict resolution skills in the areas of amicable settlement, negotiation, and reprimand. The data recorded a sub mean rating of 4.39 with a descriptive rating of High level. The item on, investigating an issue/problem in the new normal with the subordinates to find an acceptable solution had a lowest recorded mean rating of 4.39 or High level. Item 3 on, working with subordinates to find a solution to a problem in the new normal that satisfies them expectations had the highest mean rating obtained of 4.49 or High level. This implies that most of the respondents did not observe that the school head evidently provides investigation to issues before taking amicable settlement. Instead, will work with the teachers to create decisions

the satisfy expectations of others. Moreover, Table No. 2 on the area of negotiation recorded a data obtained a sub mean rating of 4.43 with a descriptive rating of High level. The item on, satisfying the needs of the subordinates with regards to conflict resolution had a lowest mean rating of 4.39 or High level. Item 2 on, conforming to the suggestions of the subordinates that may help in resolving problems had a highest mean rating of 4.49 or high level. This implies that negotiation is a valuable tool that can be used to resolve a wide range of conflicts. However, it is important to use negotiation in a way that is respectful and fair, and to consider the specific circumstances of the conflict when deciding whether or not negotiation is the best approach. Furthermore, table 2 on area, reprimand obtained a sub mean rating of 4.30 with descriptive rating of High level. Item 5 on, setting disobedient teacher/ staff as a top priority before submitting for terminal decision for grave offense to the higher office had a lowest mean rating of 4.01 or High level. Moreover, the items on, calling the attention of teacher/staff once there is a complaint from a parent or stakeholders to talk with you about it, and consulting with teacher/staff regarding a matter which could lead to a disciplinary action or suspension both recorded an obtained mean rating of 4.48 or High level. This implies that if you are considering using reprimand as a conflict management technique, it is important to weigh the potential benefits and risks. It is also important to be aware of the specific circumstances of the conflict and to tailor your approach accordingly. Table No. 2, displays school heads' level of conflict resolution skills in the areas of amicable settlement, negotiation, and reprimand. Data obtained recorded overall mean rating of 4.39 with descriptive rating of High level.

Table 3
School Heads' Level of Conflict Resolution Skills in the Area of Amicable Settlement When Grouped According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Investigates an issue/problem in the new normal with the subordinates to find an acceptable solution.	4.36	High Level	4.41	High Level
2. Integrates ideas with those of the subordinates to come up with a decision jointly.	4.39	High Level	4.45	High Level
3. Works with subordinates to find a solution to a problem in the new normal that satisfies them expectations.	4.44	High Level	4.52	Very High Level
4. Collaborates with the subordinates to come up with decisions acceptable to them.	4.50	Very High Level	4.43	High Level
5. Works with the subordinates for a proper understanding of a problem in the new normal.	4.50	Very High Level	4.43	High Level
Overall Mean	4.36	High Level	4.41	High Level

Table No. 3, reveals the school heads' level of conflict resolution skill in the area of amicable settlement when grouped according to age. As disclosed in the table the younger grouping obtained an overall mean rating of 4.36 or High level while the older grouping obtained a mean rating of 4.41 or High level respectively. A glance to the same table, item 1, on investigating an issue/ problem in the new normal with the subordinates to find an acceptable solution had obtained a lowest mean rating of 4.36 or High level from the younger grouping. However, item on, working with subordinates to find solution to a problem in the new normal that satisfies their expectations had the highest obtained mean rating of 4.52 or Very high level from the older grouping. This infers that younger teachers had a lower acuity of their school heads' conflict resolution skills than older teachers. Specifically, younger teachers had a lower perception of their school heads' ability to use amicable settlement to resolve conflicts. Also, younger teachers had a lower discernment of their school heads' ability to investigate issues and problems in the new normal with their subordinates to find an acceptable solution.

Table 4
School Heads' Level of Conflict Resolution Skills in the Area of Negotiation When Grouped According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Negotiates with subordinates so that a compromise can be reached.	4.42	High Level	4.50	Very High Level
2. Conforms to the suggestions of the subordinates that may help in resolving problems.	4.44	High Level	4.52	Very High Level
3. Proposes a middle ground for breaking deadlocks	4.31	High Level	4.45	High Level

4. Uses "give and take" so that a compromise can be made.	4.33	High Level	4.48	High Level
5. Satisfies the needs of the subordinates with regards conflict resolution.	4.36	High Level	4.41	High Level
Overall Mean	4.37	High Level	4.47	High Level

Table No. 4, exposes the school heads' level of conflict resolution skill in the area of negotiation when grouped according to age. As revealed in the table the younger grouping obtained an overall mean rating of 4.37 or High level while the older grouping obtained a mean rating of 4.47 or High level respectively. A squint to the same table, item 3, on proposing a middle ground for breaking dreadlocks had obtained a lowest mean rating of 4.31 or High level from the younger grouping. However, item on, conforming to the suggestions of the subordinates that may help in resolving problems had the highest obtained mean rating of 4.52 or Very high level form the older grouping. It can be inferred that older teachers may have a higher discernment of their school heads' conflict resolution skills, particularly in the area of conforming to the suggestions of the subordinates that may help in resolving problems.

Table 5
School Heads' Level of Conflict Resolution Skills in the Area of Reprimand When Grouped According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Calls the attention of teacher/staff once there is a complaint from a parent or stakeholders to talk with you about it.	4.39	High Level	4.55	Very High Level
2. Consults with teacher/staff regarding a matter which could lead to disciplinary action or suspension.	4.36	High Level	4.57	Very High Level
3. Initiates a private conference with teacher/staff with conflicts with colleagues.	4.17	High Level	4.61	Very High Level
4. Writes a memorandum to reprimand habitually committed errors.	3.97	High Level	4.25	High Level
5. Sets disobedient teacher/staff as top priority before submitting for terminal decision for grave offense to the higher office.	3.97	High Level	4.05	High Level
Overall Mean	4.17	High Level	4.40	High Level

Statistically, Table No. 5, divulges the school heads' level of conflict resolution skill in the area of reprimand when grouped according to age. As revealed in the table the younger grouping obtained an overall mean rating of 4.17 or High level while the older grouping obtained a mean rating of 4.40 or High level correspondingly. A cross-eyed to the same table, item 3, on initiating a private conference with teacher/staff with conflicts with colleagues had both obtained a lowest mean rating of 4.17 or High level from the younger grouping and a mean rating of 4.61 or Very high level from the older grouping respectively. This may be due to the fact that older teachers may have more experience with conflict resolution, or they may be more understanding of the need for school heads to take a proactive approach to conflict management.

Table 6
School Heads' Level of Conflict Resolution Skills in the Area of Amicable Settlement When Grouped According to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Investigates an issue/problem in the new normal with the subordinates to find an acceptable solution.	4.65	Very High Level	4.28	High Level
2. Integrates ideas with those of the subordinates to come up with a decision jointly.	4.57	Very High Level	4.37	High Level
3. Works with subordinates to find a solution to a problem in the new normal that satisfies them expectations.	4.52	Very High Level	4.47	High Level
4. Collaborates with the subordinates to come up with decisions acceptable to them.	4.70	Very High Level	4.37	High Level
5. Works with the subordinates for a	4.70	Very High Level	4.37	High Level

proper understanding of a problem in the new normal.

Overall Mean	4.65	Very High Level	4.28	High Level
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Table 6 revealed that school heads' level of conflict resolution skill in the area of amicable when grouped according to sex. As exposed in the table the male grouping obtained an overall mean rating of 4.28 or Very high level. As perceived to the same table, item 1 on, investigating an issue/problem in the new normal with the subordinates to find an acceptable solution had both obtained a lowest mean rating of 6.28or High level from the female grouping. Item on, collaborating with the decisions acceptable to them, and item on, working with the subordinates for a proper understanding of a problem in the new normal both obtained a highest mean rating of 4.70 or equivalent to Very high level from the male grouping. This implies that female teachers may be more likely to try to avoid conflict, even when it is necessary to address it. Also, female teachers are more likely to be socialized to be conflict-avoidant unlike male teachers.

Table 7
School Heads' Level of Conflict Resolution Skills in the Area of Negotiation When Grouped According to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Negotiates with subordinates so that a compromise can be reached.	4.65	Very High Level	4.39	High Level
2. Conforms to the suggestions of the subordinates that may help in resolving problems.	4.65	Very High Level	4.42	High Level
3. Proposes a middle ground for breaking deadlocks	4.48	High Level	4.35	High Level
4. Uses "give and take" so that a compromise can be made.	4.57	Very High Level	4.35	High Level
5. Satisfies the needs of the subordinates with regards conflict resolution.	4.52	Very High Level	4.33	High Level
Overall Mean	4.57	Very High Level	4.37	High Level

Table No. 7, reveals the school heads' level of conflict resolution skill in the area of negotiation when grouped according to sex. As revealed in the table the male grouping obtained an overall mean rating of 4.57 or Very high level while the female grouping obtained a mean rating of 4.37 or High level respectively. A lop-sided to the same table, item 5 on, satisfying the needs of the subordinates with regards to conflict resolution had obtained a lowest mean rating of 4.33 or High level from the female grouping. However, item on, negotiating with subordinates so that a compromise can be made had the highest obtained mean rating of 4.65 or Very high level form the male grouping. It can be inferred that male teachers may have a higher discernment of their school heads' conflict resolution skill. As implied, one possible explanation for this difference is that male teachers are more likely to be socialized, to be assertive. This means that male teachers may be more likely to stand up for themselves and their beliefs, even when it means negotiating with others. As a result, male teachers may be more likely to remark their school heads as having effective conflict resolution skills, especially in the area of negotiating with subordinates so that a compromise can be made.

Table 8
School Heads' Level of Conflict Resolution Skills in the Area of Reprimand When Grouped According to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Calls the attention of teacher/staff once there is a complaint from a parent or stakeholders to talk with you about it.	4.74	Very High Level	4.37	High Level
2. Consults with teacher/staff regarding a matter which could lead to disciplinary action or suspension.	4.65	Very High Level	4.40	High Level
3. Initiates a private conference with teacher/staff with conflicts with colleagues.	4.57	Very High Level	4.35	High Level
4. Writes a memorandum to reprimand habitually committed errors.	4.30	High Level	4.05	High Level
5. Sets disobedient teacher/staff as top priority before submitting for terminal decision for grave offense to	4.22	High Level	3.93	High Level

the higher office.

Overall Mean	4.50	Very High Level	4.22	High Level
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Table No. 8, discloses the school heads' level of conflict resolution skill in the area of reprimand when grouped according to sex. As exposed in the table the male grouping obtained an overall mean rating of 4.50 or Very high level while the female grouping obtained a mean rating of 4.22 or High level correspondingly. A bent to the same table, item 5 on, setting disobedient teacher/staff as top priority before submitting for terminal decision for grave offense to the higher office had obtained a lowest mean rating of 3.93 or High level from the female grouping. However, item on, calling the attention of teacher/staff once there is a complaint from a parent or stakeholders to talk with you about it had the highest obtained mean rating of 4.74 or Very high level form the male grouping. It can be implied that there may be a gender difference in how teachers perceive their school heads' level of conflict resolution skill in the area of reprimand. Female teachers may be more likely than male teachers to perceive their school heads as being less effective at reprimanding teachers and staff members. This may be due to the fact that female teachers are more likely to use collaborative conflict resolution styles, which may not be as effective in dealing with serious disciplinary issues. One possible explanation for this difference is that male teachers are more likely to be socialized, to be assertive.

Table 9
School Heads' Level of Conflict Resolution Skills in the Area of Amicable Settlement When Grouped According to Plantilla Position

Items	Lower Mean	Interpretation	Higher Mean	Interpretation
1. Investigates an issue/problem in the new normal with the subordinates to find an acceptable solution.	4.41	High Level	4.36	High Level
2. Integrates ideas with those of the subordinates to come up with a decision jointly.	4.54	Very High Level	4.31	High Level
3. Works with subordinates to find a solution to a problem in the new normal that satisfies them expectations.	4.49	High Level	4.49	High Level
4. Collaborates with the subordinates to come up with decisions acceptable to them.	4.51	Very High Level	4.41	High Level
5. Works with the subordinates for a proper understanding of a problem in the new normal.	4.56	Very High Level	4.36	High Level
Overall Mean	4.41	High Level	4.36	High Level

Table No. 9, unveils the school heads' level of conflict resolution skill in the area of amicable settlement when grouped according to plantilla position. As revealed in the table the lower grouping obtained an overall mean rating of 4.41 or High level while the female grouping obtained a mean rating of 4.36 or High level compatibly. A resolute to the same table, item 2 on, integrating ideas with those of the subordinates to come up with a decision jointly had obtained a lowest mean rating of 4.31 or High level from the higher grouping. Item on, working with the subordinates for a proper understanding of a problem in the new normal had the highest obtained mean rating of 4.56 or Very high level form the lower grouping. This infers that the possible explanation for this difference is that teachers in lower plantilla positions may be more likely to rely on their school heads for support and guidance. This is because teachers in lower plantilla positions may have less experience and may not have the same level of authority as teachers in higher plantilla positions. As a result, teachers in lower plantilla positions may be more likely to appreciate school heads who are willing to work with them to resolve conflicts and to find solutions to problems.

Table 10
School Heads' Level of Conflict Resolution Skills in the Area of Negotiation When Grouped According to Plantilla Position

Items	Lower Mean	Interpretation	Higher Mean	Interpretation
1. Negotiates with subordinates so that a compromise can be reached.	4.56	Very High Level	4.36	High Level
2. Conforms to the suggestions of the subordinates that may help in resolving problems.	4.56	Very High Level	4.41	High Level
3. Proposes a middle ground for breaking deadlocks	4.44	High Level	4.33	High Level

4. Uses "give and take" so that a compromise can be made.	4.54	Very High Level	4.28	High Level
5. Satisfies the needs of the subordinates with regards conflict resolution.	4.39	High Level	4.38	High Level
Overall Mean	4.50	Very High Level	4.35	High Level

Table No. 10, shows the school heads' level of conflict resolution skill in the area of amicable settlement when grouped according to plantilla position. As exposed in the table the lower grouping obtained an overall mean rating of 4.50 or Very high level while the higher grouping obtained a mean rating of 4.35 or High level. A stance to the same table, item 4 on, using "give and take" so that a compromise can be made had obtained a lowest mean rating of 4.28 or High level from the higher grouping. Items on, negotiating with subordinates so that a compromise can be reached and conforming with the suggestions of the subordinates that may help in resolving problems both had the highest obtained mean rating of 4.56 or Very high level from the lower grouping. This accomplishes that teachers in higher plantilla positions may have more to lose if they compromise.

Table 11

School Heads' Level of Conflict Resolution Skills in the Area of Reprimand When Grouped According to Plantilla Position

Items	Lower Mean	Interpretation	Higher Mean	Interpretation
1. Calls the attention of teacher/staff once there is a complaint from a parent or stakeholders to talk with you about it.	4.46	High Level	4.49	High Level
2. Consults with teacher/staff regarding a matter which could lead to disciplinary action or suspension.	4.51	Very High Level	4.44	High Level
3. Initiates a private conference with teacher/staff with conflicts with colleagues.	4.41	High Level	4.41	High Level
4. Writes a memorandum to reprimand habitually committed errors.	4.20	High Level	4.05	High Level
5. Sets disobedient teacher/staff as top priority before submitting for terminal decision for grave offense to the higher office.	3.90	High Level	4.13	High Level
Overall Mean	4.30	High Level	4.30	High Level

Table No. 11, exemplifies the school heads' level of conflict resolution skill in the area of reprimand when grouped according to plantilla position. As showing in the table the lower and higher groupings both obtained an overall mean rating of 4.30 equivalent to High level. A resolute to the same table, item 4 on, writing a memorandum to reprimand habitually committed errors had obtained a lowest mean rating of 4.05 or High level from the higher grouping. Item 2 on, consulting with teacher/ staff regarding a matter which could lead to disciplinary action or suspension had the highest obtained mean rating of 4.51 or Very high level from the lower grouping.

Table 12

School Heads' Level of Conflict Resolution Skills in the Area of Amicable Settlement When Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Items	Lower Mean	Interpretation	Higher Mean	Interpretation
1. Investigates an issue/problem in the new normal with the subordinates to find an acceptable solution.	4.48	High Level	4.10	High Level
2. Integrates ideas with those of the subordinates to come up with a decision jointly.	4.50	Very High Level	4.20	High Level
3. Works with subordinates to find a solution to a problem in the new normal that satisfies them expectations.	4.55	Very High Level	4.30	High Level
4. Collaborates with the subordinates to come up with decisions acceptable to them.	4.55	Very High Level	4.20	High Level

5. Works with the subordinates for a proper understanding of a problem in the new normal.	4.50	Very High Level	4.35	High Level
Overall Mean	4.48	High Level	4.10	High Level

Table No. 12 unveils the school heads' level of conflict resolution skill in the area of amicable settlement when grouped according to highest educational attainment. As revealed in the table, the lower grouping obtained an overall mean rating of 4.48 or High level while the female grouping obtained a mean rating of 4.10 or High level. A stance to the same table, item 1 on, investigating an issue/problem in the new normal with the subordinates to find an acceptable solution had obtained a lowest mean rating of 4.10 or High level. Items on, working with the subordinates for a proper understanding of a problem in the new normal and collaborating with the subordinates to come up with decisions acceptable to them both had the highest obtained mean rating of 4.55 or Very high level from the lower grouping. This implies that teachers with higher educational attainment may have a lower perception of school heads' conflict resolution skill in the area of investigating an issue/problem in the new normal with the subordinates to find an acceptable solution. This may be because teachers with higher educational attainment may have a better understanding of conflict resolution and may have higher expectations for their school heads. As a result, teachers with higher educational attainment may be more likely to be critical of school heads' conflict resolution skills.

Table 13

School Heads' Level of Conflict Resolution Skills in the Area of Negotiation When Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Items	Lower Mean	Interpretation	Higher Mean	Interpretation
1. Negotiates with subordinates so that a compromise can be reached.	4.58	Very High Level	4.10	High Level
2. Conforms to the suggestions of the subordinates that may help in resolving problems.	4.58	Very High Level	4.20	High Level
3. Proposes a middle ground for breaking deadlocks	4.50	Very High Level	4.05	High Level
4. Uses "give and take" so that a compromise can be made.	4.48	High Level	4.20	High Level
5. Satisfies the needs of the subordinates with regards conflict resolution.	4.43	High Level	4.25	High Level
Overall Mean	4.52	Very High Level	4.16	High Level

Table No. 13 displays the school heads' level of conflict resolution skill in the area of negotiation when grouped according to highest educational attainment. As revealed in the table the lower grouping obtained an overall mean rating of 4.52 or Very high level while the higher grouping obtained a mean rating of 4.16 or High level. Item 3 on, proposing a middle ground for breaking deadlocks had obtained a lowest mean rating of 4.05 or High level from the higher grouping. Items on, negotiating with subordinates so that a compromise can be reached and conforming with the suggestions of the subordinates that may help in resolving problems both had the highest obtained mean rating of 4.58 or Very high level from the lower grouping.

Table 14

School Heads' Level of Conflict Resolution Skills in the Area of Reprimand When Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Items	Lower Mean	Interpretation	Higher Mean	Interpretation
1. Calls the attention of teacher/staff once there is a complaint from a parent or stakeholders to talk with you about it.	4.53	Very High Level	4.30	High Level
2. Consults with teacher/staff regarding a matter which could lead to disciplinary action or suspension.	4.60	Very High Level	4.10	High Level
3. Initiates a private conference with teacher/staff with conflicts with colleagues.	4.52	Very High Level	4.10	High Level
4. Writes a memorandum to reprimand habitually committed errors.	4.25	High Level	3.75	High Level
5. Sets disobedient teacher/staff as	4.02	High Level	4.00	High Level

top priority before submitting for terminal decision for grave offense to the higher office.

Overall Mean **4.38** **High Level** **4.05** **High Level**

Table No. 14 illustrates the school heads' level of conflict resolution skill in the area of reprimand when grouped according to highest educational attainment. As illustrated in the table lower grouping obtained an overall mean rating of 4.38 equivalent to High level and the higher grouping obtained an overall mean rating of 4.05 or High level. Item 5 on, setting disobedient teacher/staff as top priority before submitting decision for terminal decision for grave offense to the higher office had obtained a lowest mean rating of 4.00 or High level from the higher grouping. Item 2 on, consulting with teacher/ staff regarding a matter which could lead to disciplinary action or suspension had the highest obtained mean rating of 4.60 or Very high level form the lower grouping.

Table 15
Level of Teacher's Performance during the School Year-2022

Variable	N	Mean	Interpretation
Teacher's Performance	80	4.380	Very Satisfactory

Table 15 reveals the level of teacher's performance during the school year 2022-2023. Survey questionnaire containing the profile of the teachers was utilized in gathering data. As for the profile, it was found that teachers with Teacher 1 position, 1 to 5 years teaching experiences, no units in master's degree and not undergo trainings relevant to the subjects they were handling were dominated among respondents. Meanwhile, their teaching performance with 4.380 computed mean revealed Very Satisfactory.

Conclusions

Most of the respondents were older than 35 who work as teachers in position 1, are female, and possess a bachelor's degree. This finding implies that teachers can dominate the research arena regardless of their didactic achievements if they are mature and consistently capable of doing well in any role. When grouped and compared based on age, the school heads demonstrated a high degree of conflict resolution proficiency in the areas of peaceful settlement, negotiation, and reprimand. As a result, there is a complicated relationship between age and conflict resolution method that depends on a number of variables, including the personality and experience of the school head as well as the particular dispute situation. However, when put together, the school heads' proficiency in negotiation, amicable settlement, and reprimand. There is no significant difference in age and sex when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. On the other hand, it resulted in a significant difference when collected and compared according to the plantilla position and, therefore, the highest educational attainment. This means that the status of the plantilla and the level of education predict the conflict resolution skills of school heads. Other factors such as personality, experience and education may also play a role. Therefore, staffing status and educational level are important factors in determining the conflict resolution skills of school principals. School head's with higher staffing status and higher education are more likely to be effective conflict resolvers. Although there was no significant relationship between the conflict management skills of school heads and teacher performance. It follows that they cannot prove that there is no causal relationship between these factors. It is possible that a causal relationship exists, but it was not observed in these studies. Additionally, it is also important to note that these studies were conducted under specific conditions and in specific populations. It is possible that the results will be different in other settings or other populations. Additionally, it is important to consider all of these factors when trying to improve teacher performance: teacher education, teacher experience, teacher support, and the student factor.

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